

Disciplinary Commons in TCS

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1 Context

The MSc in Scientific Computing and Data Analysis (MISCADA) was launched in Durham in 2019 to replace some other masters programs that were heavily outdated and of lesser quality. The program caters to students who likely haven't studied Computer Science, yet have some knowledge and affinity of it, most likely through a first degree in some other science.

The Advanced Algorithms submodule sits as a half part of a wider module which has had a variety of names over the years and which is currently called Advanced Algorithms and Discrete Systems. The curriculum is taught by lecturers who work in Theoretical Computer Science (TCS) and have a background in mathematics. A typical yearly intake for MISCADA is about 60 of which some 10-30 take Advanced Algorithms and Discrete Systems.

The students come from a variety of backgrounds. Some come from Durham, where they previously studied another (usually science) degree. The vast majority of the rest are students from outside of the UK, many of which come from the far east. The quality of the students and their level of engagement is mixed. It was known that sometimes new masters programs take a few years to warm up, with the average quality of the students increasing in the first few years. My personal impression of MISCADA is that we can still improve this quality.

Advanced Algorithms and Discrete Systems sits in the MISCADA program as a rare theoretical module. It is one of only two from nine where the other is Computational Linear Algebra and Continuous Systems. Advanced Algorithms and Discrete Systems breaks down naturally into the two equally weighted and eponymously named submodules. Each of these then splits into two equally weighted parts. Advanced Algorithms and Discrete Systems was formed from four lecturers in TCS coming together to teach material that gives a flavour of TCS. These lecturers, of which I was one, were given a free hand in the creation of the curriculum. Advanced Algorithms is formed from my material on Introduction to Algorithms, together with material from Dr. Tom Friedetzky on Randomized Algorithms.

Although the lecturers have a background in theory, the MISCADA program is not about theory. Indeed, it is quite the opposite, as witnessed by the density of theoretical modules. We believed from the start that we needed to

integrate some practice into the Advanced Algorithms curriculum. It was always my intention to make my part an introduction to not just algorithms, but also computational complexity, which is my research area. I already had a background of teaching SAT-solving and writing (basic) SAT-solvers, so it seemed natural to me to bring this into the curriculum. Indeed, this fits nicely with an introduction to NP-completeness which would usually be through the Satisfiability (SAT) problem and its ability to encode (polynomially) a (polynomially-bounded) non-deterministic Turing Machine.

2 Content

Let us recall that Advanced Algorithms sits in a Scientific Computing masters program as a semimodule within Advanced Algorithms and Discrete Systems. It is taught the first of the two. The curriculum is intended for people with a degree in some science but likely not Computer Science. It is as far as conceivable from comprehensive. It is a whistlestop tour of concepts that arise in the understanding of Computational Complexity. It would perhaps better have been labelled as a course in Computational Complexity.

In order to understand computational complexity at all it is imperative to understand something about the concepts of algorithm and model of computation. We begin with the algorithms. When I set the curriculum, I wanted to consider just what was strictly necessary to understand the concept of algorithm, but in a reasonably formal way. Therefore we begin with computational problems, for which it is necessary to have some alphabet. I begin, as one would expect, with a finite alphabet. A peculiarity of the course, is that I show the students how concepts that we begin with are quickly lost when we generalise in order to capture natural situations. For example, in the first non-trivial algorithms that we study, for the sorting problem (e.g. on natural numbers) each number is usually considered an atomic entity despite that in reality it must be encoded, e.g. in binary. The tension between the theoretical and the practical is deliberately woven into the course. The first computational problems we meet, however, are over an alphabet of 0 and 1; or perhaps 0, 1 and blank. The first problem is about (recognising) Palindromes. Here there is no particular need for a blank symbol. The second problem is Binary Addition. This doesn't need a blank symbol, unless we are working on a single tape, and this is the first time we address the model of computation. Having met a basic notion of algorithm we proceed to address the complexity of these algorithms. This raises the question as to what is a single step of the algorithm. For example, can we move from one end of the input to the other end in a single step? This drops the complexity of Palindromes from $\Theta(n^2)$ to $O(n)$. A similar question arises in the analysis of Binary Addition, for example on a three tape Turing machine this complexity is $O(\log n)$, but this rises to $\Theta(\log^2(n))$ on a single tape machine.

The second lecture begins with (list) Sorting and this is usually given over some infinite alphabet. Thus, we appear to abandon a fundamental principle that we just learnt. We contrast two algorithms for Sorting. The first is the

naive in-place version of Insertion-Sort which runs in $O(n^2)$. The second is the more sophisticated, divide-and-conquer (recursive) algorithm Merge-Sort. I wanted to cover a naive and an optimal algorithm. Given the time constraints, I only wanted to cover two algorithms, and this is how I arrived at my choice. I actually show the two Sorting algorithms in MATLAB, despite that the course prefers the use of Python. This is because, on Rosetta Code, there was a sub-optimal implementation in MATLAB that appears to annul the time advantage of Merge-Sort by using a single command whose implementation is particularly expensive. Through this, I again emphasise the gap between theory and practice.

I use a single-tape Turing Machine (TM) as my basic model of computation and I use the Java simulator Tursi to show the machinations of a TM, e.g. on Palindromes. Then it is natural for me to define (propositional) Satisfiability (SAT) and the reduction from a polynomial-time bounded non-deterministic TM to SAT. I give a minimalist presentation of this that is formally rigorous. This allows me to show other NP-complete problem, such as (graph) 3-Colourability, together with its reduction from SAT.

It has been desired that the Advanced Algorithms course not be wholly theoretical, so at this point I move in a new direction, albeit one that naturally follows - we look at modern implementations of SAT-solvers. We start with the standard DPLL (David-Putmans-Logemann-Loveland) especially in its simplest recursive formulation. We then focus on clause learning and present an imperative formulation of the CDCL (Conflict Driven Clause Learning) modification. SAT-solving traditionally forms the backbone of the coursework and gives the course a practical aspect. Typically, the students solve chromatic number on some graphs presented as a text file with pairs of vertices on each line for edges.

The final part of the curriculum feels like an addendum, mostly likely because it is. Depending on the time we spend on SAT-solving and CDCL, there may be little time for it, and it never appears in the coursework. It concerns another fundamental problem - clustering. We study two clustering algorithms of distinct types - the first hierarchical and the second non-hierarchical. We work with examples on bottom-up, agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering and the second algorithm we present is the centroid-based k-Means Algorithms.

The backbone of the curriculum is thus set in the order Algorithms, Complexity, NP-completeness, SAT and SAT-solving, together with a minimum of concepts that are needed to comprehend these. I do not use a textbook and I usually recommend Christos Papadimitriou's Computational Complexity for further reading. Whilst this book is somewhat out of date now, it remains current in the concepts encountered in the course. I would be motivated to change any aspect that the students particularly dislike. Usually, when I introduce graph colouring, I do so motivated by the classical map colouring problem. I tend to give a brief proof of the classical 5-Colour Theorem on the way, largely because it was proved by Percy Heawood from Durham in the 19th century. Obviously, this doesn't play a pivotal role, but the international students often appreciate the local connection. The final part of the course, on clustering algorithms, could easily be substituted for something else. One possibility is

to continue the theme of application and run through a basic recursive Python implementation of DPLL. Although, in other courses, I set the writing of a SAT-solver as the coursework, in Advanced Algorithms, I have limited this to the use of a SAT-solver. However, I am open to any ideas from the floor!

3 Methods and Philosophy

The curriculum for Advanced Algorithms is delivered in a lecture/ seminar style in which the students are encouraged to participate. However, they are often reluctant to participate and this results in something more akin to a lecture. The principal characteristic of the course is that a lot is packed in a small amount of time, it is a whistlestop tour. This is the reason that practicals do not play a role, as they require a lot of time. If there were more time, then surely practicals would be integrated into the course. In particular, this would make sense for the applied parts of the course, I think especially of SAT-solving and programming of Turing Machines. Experimenting with the programming of basic Turing Machines is one of my favourite ways to get into the theory of computation but it is time-consuming. It would likely eat an entire hour of my course, which is only eight hours in length.

The teaching of this course is slide-based with the exception of a detour to the blackboard to prove the 5-Colour Theorem for Planar Graphs. This is a weaker form of the celebrated 4-Colour Theorem, that has a relatively simple proof. It is not strictly relevant to algorithmics. I present it largely because I am already discussing graph colouring (from an algorithmic perspective) and the 5-Colour Theorem was proved by a Durham academic in Victorian times. Indeed, Percy Heawood proved it while demonstrating a bug in Alfred Kempe's (apocryphal) proof of the 4-Colour Theorem. The international students often especially warm to some local connections.

The slides are informative rather than playful. I think I favour more playful slides with more junior years but by the time of a masters the student should be acclimatised to serious study. I try to keep the slides uncluttered but there are many technical details (for example, in the reduction of a polynomial-time NTM to SAT). The slides contain few diagrams but I frequently change the colour of text to highlight salient parts of the discourse.

In sample discussions of methods and philosophy of teaching, the discourse is rather idealistic. Yet most courses suffer from the effects of pragmatism when they are finally created. That is, the ideal course that we dream of may be far removed from the course that we end up creating when we factor in the teacher's constraints and the timetabling constraints. It begs the question as to how much room there is for a teaching philosophy in the creation of a course. However, every course (ideal or hurriedly put together) still has its methods.

In terms of a teaching philosophy, if it is guided by one, it is not fundamentally constructivist. I have my doubts about the over-use of constructivism in the sciences, especially the mathematical sciences. How many versions of the truth are there? In terms of computer programming, constructivism makes

more sense, as programming is a fundamentally constructive task (and there are multiple solutions). I don't teach any programming in my module, other than the use of SAT-solvers. However, the assessment involves a programming task, to reduce Graph Colouring to SAT instances, and then solve them in a SAT-solver. The general guiding philosophy of the course is essentially realist, and might be seen as a form of behaviourism.

4 Assessment

4.1 Purpose of assessment

As this is a masters course, the students will be very familiar with assessment as a device to ensure learning as well as to evaluate quality. The curriculum is built so that only the first seven from eight hours of teaching is assessed because it may be necessary to drop the last topic of clustering if the earlier topics take longer than expected. For example, this happened in the present academic year. The Advanced Algorithms part of the module, of which I teach the first half, is largely theoretical. I have insinuated SAT-solving into the curriculum in order to give it a more applied edge. This allows me to base part of the Advanced Algorithms coursework around SAT-solving and this involves some programming tasks with Python which form the applied part of the coursework.

4.2 Structure of the assessment

The Advanced Algorithms assessment is by a single piece of coursework usually released halfway through the teaching. At this point, my half of the course, think of it as Algorithms and Complexity, is finished. The next half of the course is Randomised Algorithms and is about to begin. The coursework is equally split between these two components, so the students are ready to work on my half at the release point, if not yet the other half. The coursework involves a series of questions testing the students' knowledge of concepts they have learnt as well as how to comprehend new variants of these concepts that they may see for the first time in the assessment. In this sense the questions have to do with comprehension and application, as they can always confer with the slides on questions of knowledge. My part of the assessment involves some basic programming tasks notwithstanding that there is no teaching of programming in the module. They are expected to have some background in programming and I do show certain examples of a computer solving problems, for example for Sorting and SAT-solving. I restrict the students to use Python.

4.3 Content of the assessment

I usually begin the assessment with some relatively straightforward computational tasks to be performed by the student on paper rather than on a computer. A typical exercise might involve graph metrics such as chromatic number, independence number or clique number of some simple graphs on fewer than 10

vertices. This is not because these graph metrics are important, rather it is to test the student's understanding, especially as I usually define some variants of the metric that the students see for the first time in the coursework. This tests how well the students comprehend something new that they did not already see in class.

The next part of the assessment concerns calculating some of these metrics using a SAT-solver on some larger instances (> 30 vertices) where it would not be feasible for the students to attempt this on paper. If it involves graphs, then these would be given in text files as a series of lines each of which has two numbers x and y separated by a space. This indicates the presence of the edge (x,y) in the graph and they may assume that all vertices appear in some edge. In order for the students to process these in Python, they need to write some code to read them, for example, into a package like `networkx`. This is the first task. The second task is to produce SAT-instances, generally more than one per graph, whose testing in some off-the-shelf SAT-solver will calculate the graph metric. For example, for chromatic number, one produces instances of the form `graph-has-a-3-colouring`, `graph-has-a-4-colouring` etc. so that the answer is given by the point at which the solution turns from UNSAT to SAT. The students are not told that they need to produce multiple SAT instances. They need to work it out for themselves. That said, and this applies also to the comprehension of variant graph metrics, I do allow them to question me during the coursework. I give guidance but not the answer. However, if they figure out the right approach, I will give some signal that indeed they are on the right path.

My final part of the coursework asks the students to give algorithms for some problems that are variants of what they already met in the lectures and comment on the computational complexity of these algorithms. Typically, some problem is in P and another is NP-hard. The crux here is usually to understand the huge performance gap between an algorithm of the form n^c (c is a constant) versus another of c^n . I am not confident all of the students succeed in comprehending this.

Then comes the second half of the coursework on Randomised Algorithms.

4.4 Plagiarism problems

We traditionally had no plagiarism problems on this course but we plan to use MOSS and Gradescope on future code submissions.

4.5 Feedback

My part of Advanced Algorithms is usually fitted into a single question in five parts. For example, the graph metrics solved on paper form the first part. I provide feedback individually for each of the five parts, together with the mark. The first part usually has around 20 individual answers and I do not give an exhaustive list of which are right and wrong, but rather an indication of where the errors were, as they are usually grouped (e.g. multiple errors in clique number). Here is an example of some feedback.

Example 1.

Q1.

- a. 8/10. Errors in Star Colouring number for 1-3 and Acyclic Colouring number in 4.
- b. 9/18. Answers correct but code looks problematic. For colouring it seems to be based on an assumption that the number of colours is 4. For clique number nothing SAT-like is being built.
- c. 5/7. Correct except the algorithm is much more efficient than the factorial of the number of edges!
- d. 7/7.
- e. 0/8. The question is about star colouring not acyclic colouring. Should the “at least 3” be “at most 3”?

Total: 29/50.

Example 2.

Q1.

- a. 8/10. Errors for Star Colouring number for 3-5 and Acyclic Colouring number in 2-3.
- b. 18/18.
- c. 7/7.
- d. 7/7.
- e. 8/8.

General comment: Outstanding.

Total: 48/50

I omit feedback sometimes when the answer is fully correct. The reader may have a feeling of the feedback being given to justify the mark. It seems that this is as important to the marker as allowing the student to learn from the feedback for the future. Knowing that this summative coursework concludes the course can only reinforce this feeling. I am always happy to meet students after the marks are returned, and the course is finished, to give finer and deeper feedback. Very few students are interested in this, except where it may alter their mark. I don't publicise that this is possible, but I have amended marks where students have petitioned me as having not understood something in their submission. This usually applies to some submitted code that doesn't run but that they subsequently persuade me makes some limited sense. Here is an example of this happening.

Q1.

- a. 2/10. The answers are labelled Figure 1 and Figure 2, but Figure 1 has two graphs and Figure 2 has three graphs - which of these are being referred to? For Figure 1, the results are correct for Graph 1. For Figure 2, the answer is wrong for all the graphs.
- b. 0/18. No attempt.
- c. 6/7. A bit vague in the complexity evaluation.
- d. 3/7. Very vague about rings.
- e. 0/8. No attempt.

Total: 11/50

On questioning 1b upgraded to 4/18 as some code submitted.

New total: 15/50

5 Summary of Curriculum

1. Introduction to Algorithms
 - Alphabets, Tapes and Steps of computation
 - Time and Space Complexity
 - Asymptotic notation
2. Sorting
 - Insertion-Sort
 - Merge-Sort
 - Gap between theory and practice
3. Graph Colouring
 - Introduction to Graphs
 - Graph and map colouring
 - Heawood and the 5-Colour Theorem
 - Algorithms for 2-Colouring and 3-Colouring
4. SAT and NP-completeness
 - Turing Machines
 - Propositional Satisfiability (SAT)
 - Reduction of NP to SAT
 - Other NP-complete problems: 3-Colouring
5. SAT-Solving
 - DPLL
 - Clause learning
 - Solving problems with SAT-solvers

6. Clustering

- Hierarchical Clustering
- k -Means Clustering